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EXPLORING QUALITY IN EU FUNDED ENGINEERING EDUCATION PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

It is a requirement of Engineering Education Projects funded as part of the EU ERASMUS+ Programme to have a Quality Work Package as part of their project structure. On the surface this would appear an eminently sensible requirement, yet interpretations and implementation of this work package can often be confusing and challenging for project teams. Understanding what is required also links into the wider questions of what does Quality in Engineering Education really look like and how can the Quality Work Package help to drive the project thinking with respect to the sustainability and ongoing use of the project outcomes.

These issues will be explored within the context of a current ERASMUS+ Capacity Building Project called EXTEND. The project is seeking to develop the next generation of Engineering Educators in the Russian Federation and Tajikistan and is supported by partners from Romania, Latvia, Portugal and the UK. The coming together of 12 very different higher education institutions around a common goal has exposed how diverse a range of approaches to the subject of 'quality' there are when considering engineering education projects.

The paper will share the methodology adopted within this particular project and consider it with respect to the wider EU funded Engineering Education Project landscape.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Quality is a word that is common in the vocabulary of those of us engaged in engineering education. The question is - do we know what it means? When we refer to quality, are we clear about the context and are we consistent with what we mean? The contention of this paper is that when we refer to the quality of engineering education projects, such as those funded through the EU Erasmus+ Programme [1], we need a more robust understanding of what quality actually refers to and what it is seeking to achieve.

When engineering education projects receive funding to enable their execution, it is important that the project achieves its stated outcomes. This is generally ensured through sound project management so where does quality appear in this scenario? In Erasmus+ Projects there are generally two identified work packages, one for Project Management and one for Quality. How these work together and what the 'quality goals' are form the subject of this paper.

2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE

When we consider quality, the context is of considerable importance.

The Cambridge English Dictionary definition of quality is 'how good or bad something is' or 'a high standard' [2]. These are a helpful starting point but vague when we consider the engineering education contexts we work in. In order to explore this further, three different contexts will be considered and discussed. These are

- Quality in Engineering
- Quality in Projects
- Quality in Higher Education.

2.1 Quality in Engineering

As engineers, the idea of quality forms an integral part of our education and training. We are introduced to the idea of quality engineering and its foundation, the quality system, at a very early stage [3]. The work of Deming and colleagues is the foundation on which many ideas have been developed. The focus on the optimisation of product quality through effective design, manufacturing and checking processes with inbuilt feedback loops to enable the early detection and rectification of problems and the continuous improvement of the whole system is the fundamental objective. Over time, the development of numerous tools and techniques has allowed the system and the decisions it promotes to be based on clear evidence of performance in a numerical form. This builds confidence and enables continuous improvement to be driven from an informed position.

Quality Engineering has matured into an important discipline within the broader engineering context and has been extended beyond the initial 'product' focus to address 'service' industry scenarios as well. For example, designing and manufacturing a laptop produces a tangible 'product', whereas the repair of a laptop represents a 'service'. The ISO 9000 Standard along with methodologies like Six Sigma have resulted in a well-defined and robust discipline.

2.2 Quality in Projects

The project is a fundamental building block of industry today. Many engineers find that project management can form a significant component of their job responsibilities as their career progresses, so understanding what quality means in the project context is important.

The starting point for project quality is the Iron Triangle – the coming together of three key elements of a project [4]. These elements, the specification, the budget and the time available, need to be known and monitored throughout the lifetime of the project. The aim is to achieve the required tangible output within the identified financial budget and in the time period that is available. These ideas are the foundation of project management and are explained in all standard texts.

Over time the approaches to ensuring project quality i.e. the fulfilment of the stated needs in the Iron Triangle, have developed and today's project manager can apply different techniques to build confidence that a project will reach a successful outcome, an example being Earned Value Analysis. Similar to the ISO Standard for quality engineering, project management is guided by Bodies of Knowledge such as that produced by the UK Association for Project Management [5].

What we can notice in the two contexts discussed so far is that although initially the attempt is made to identify and use numerical evidence to demonstrate performance and support decision making, inevitably as we move to service quality and the adherence to specification elements, elements of subjectivity and less well defined measures of quality are introduced. In both cases though, the meaning of quality is firmly rooted in the idea that 'something meets a required need'.

If we consider the educational context, what we are presented with is a more complex scenario.

2.3 Quality in Higher Education

The Higher Education context is less able to rely on numerical data when assessing quality. Student and teacher experiences and perceptions are critical to understanding quality. These by their very nature are qualitative in nature and despite the numerous attempts to quantify them through end of course reviews and national surveys such as the National Student Survey in the UK, they need to be explored carefully in order to ensure the correct understanding is reached and decisions made.

We refer to quality as having two parts – Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Enhancement (QE). Both are focused on the quality of student learning, which is the primary focus of any university [6]. Assurance is about ensuring the processes, infrastructure, content and personnel are in place to enable each and every student to realise their educational potential. In all parts of the world this is guided by agencies of Government that are tasked to demonstrate that identified standards are being met. For example the Quality Assurance Agency is that body in the UK. In assurance there is often a blend of quantitative and qualitative components, but the picture is more nuanced than say the delivery of a manufactured product [7].

Quality enhancement is the process of continuous improvement identified earlier. Decisions are made in this space based on QA data but also as a result of strategic imperatives, the need for change and the ambition of teaching teams and individuals. As can be imagined, this is not well defined, will vary from context to context and is often based on a variety of evidence. Having said that it is enhancement that has impact and adds value, yet too often it is a secondary consideration after assurance [8].

2.4 Synthesis and application to Erasmus+

It is based on a consideration of the three prior sections that we now consider how these characteristics are synthesised and applied to Erasmus+ projects. Erasmus+ projects are chosen as the focus for this work as, in recent years, this element of the European Union research funding has been the most supportive of projects in engineering education. Focused on the generation, dissemination and implementation of new ideas and practices that strengthen engineering education in the EU and beyond. Yet often these 'new approaches' don't have a marked impact across the community. Educators often come across ideas in an ad hoc way and the more far reaching impact is rarely felt. It is the contention of this work that part of the reason for this is that the Quality Framework applied within Erasmus+ projects, being left to project teams to define, lacks the focus and coherency to realise the impactful outcomes that justify the initial financial investment.

Considering the criteria used by reviewers of submitted Erasmus+ applications there is much scope for different interpretations of the nature of quality when applied to these projects [9]. This lack of clarity is then manifested in the variety of Quality Plans that are produced for the said projects. Taking two examples, the projects HARMONY [10] and EU-Mong [11], we see a range of commonly repeated features which suggest that the interpretation of quality is not consistent. In addition to the range of different terminologies used, the overlap between project management and quality and the reliance on numerical data, there is no focus on the lasting impact of the project outcomes, the ultimate measure of project quality.

2.5 Final thoughts

The brief exploration of the background topics that can influence the success or not of an engineering education project suggest that a more coherent and structured approach to the consideration of the Quality Work Package in projects would be of benefit. That way the return on the work conducted in terms of its impact across the European engineering education community would be enhanced.

3 APPROACH TO THE STUDY

This work is aimed at initiating a discussion within the European Engineering Education community around how we can work together to ensure a more effective translation of ideas and results from Erasmus+ projects to a broader cross-section of institutions such that the learning becomes embedded. The approach taken here has been to consider two case study examples that the authors have been participants in. The projects, their approach and the learning are explored to enable the articulation of an initial Project Quality Framework. This is very much viewed as a

starting point and that a broader exploration of past and current approaches is needed to better substantiate the draft Framework. This will form the next phase of the work.

4 CASE STUDIES

4.1 Case 1 – QAEMarketPlace4HEI (QAEMP)

This project (now completed) focused on ways to enhance the quality of engineering education by considering how QA and QE can work effectively together. The common theme was the partners' mutual interest in active learning, in particular the application of the CDIO (Conceive Design Implement Operate) framework [12] [13]. The partner universities were from Iceland, Finland, Denmark, Sweden, France and the UK.

When reading the detail of the Quality Work Package for QAEMP, the focus is primarily on the achievement of milestones, which, as has been stated before, is a project management task rather than a quality one. This allied to the need to prepare reports leaves little capacity to explore the real learning that is taking place and how this can then be translated into more widespread visibility and impact across the sector.

The lack of focus in the Quality space resulted in little 'continuous improvement' during the project implementation and consequently no significant lessons learned as a result of the journey each member experienced.

Although in terms of the ideas generated and the work conducted during the project lifetime, especially in the area of self-evaluation, the project was deemed a success, the extent to which the project has impacted the sector is minimal, even within the project partner institutions. With a more clearly defined and structured Quality Work Package the result could have been very different.

4.2 Case 2 – EXTEND

The EXTEND project (still in progress) is aimed at modernising the approaches used in teaching the engineering disciplines in Russia and Tajikistan. By increasing the quality of education through effective teacher education it is hoped to make engineering education more attractive, improve students' motivation and improve the possibilities of employment for young engineers [14]. The partner universities were from Russia, Tajikistan, Romania, Latvia, Portugal and the UK.

The EXTEND Quality Plan is constructed with 5 key points guiding. They are that it

- Is outcomes focused
- Works alongside Project Management
- Needs to be thorough but not overly bureaucratic
- Focuses on 'value of project activity' more so than compliance with the plan
- Is accepting of justified change.

In terms of the activity focus, three areas of work have been identified:

- A thorough review of each project meeting and the team operation
- Co-ordinating the setting up and operation of the External Quality Control Team
- Evaluating the quality and value of the project outputs.

Of these three areas of work, it is the latter that is considered the most important with two elements the focus:

- A review of the documentation produced to ascertain its value as a coherent and high quality record of the project as it was undertaken
- A review of the quality and value of the individual EXTEND Centres for Engineering Educator training.

In the case of this project, the Centres are the main output and it is their reach, impact and sustainability that will need to be evaluated to demonstrate success. A Rating Statement for each Centre that identifies areas of positive value and areas for development, alongside a description of the local context is a starting point.

One of the main challenges in these projects has been the overlap between work packages and the clarity in understanding where responsibility lies. Since projects adopt a work package approach with explicit responsibilities allocated in the form of work package leaders, there needs to be a clear and shared understanding as to how these will operate side by side. Often the Project Management, Quality and Dissemination work packages can have conflicting or overlapping tasks and the successful execution comes down to how well the team works together rather than due to having a robust framework in place. This was identified in the literature and experienced in both case study projects.

5 DISCUSSION

From both the background literature and the case study examples, it can be seen that the approach taken towards the Quality Work Package in Erasmus+ projects is variable. As a consequence the following ideas are offered as a starting point in the journey towards a more standard Project Quality Framework.

The initial proposal identifies three areas where the focus of the Quality work needs to be directed

- Quality of the Project Journey
- Quality of the Project Outcomes
- Quality of the Project Impact.

Explaining these in turn

a) Quality of the Project Journey

This would focus on the experience of the project participants. How valuable the various interactions are e.g. project meetings (face-to-face and online). The effectiveness of the project leadership. The important consideration here is not to get confused with the Project Management work package responsibilities. It is not about the achievement of deliverables but the effectiveness of the team in achieving the said deliverables.

b) Quality of the Project Outcomes

The focus here would be on what has been produced as a consequence of the project. This would consider the tangible outputs such as reports, papers and processes along with the quality and extent of the sharing of these outputs. The important consideration here is not to get confused with the Dissemination work package responsibilities. It is not simply about numbers but also the reach and the connections that are realised as a consequence of the work undertaken.

c) Quality of the Project Impact

To a large extent this would bring the previous two elements together and explore the ways in which the experience and outcomes are to be maximised in terms of the partner institutions and the wider engineering education community. This suggests that sustainability should be a part of the Quality thinking and that the project team should be required to demonstrate impact at an agreed point in time after the conclusion of the project work. This enhancement focused requirement would be an important step towards demonstrating the value of the funder investment in the project.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents some initial thoughts about how to better embed Quality thinking into Erasmus+ projects such that they are more able to demonstrate a wider impact beyond the project team. Through the implementation of a more structured and robust Project Framework with a requirement of the team beyond the stated duration of the project, the return on the project can be better demonstrated and a greater clarity of responsibility can be afforded during the project execution.

As a concept paper, this argument is presented in order to initiate a conversation. The next steps would be to explore more Erasmus+ Quality Work Package and project impact evidence and then to use this to further develop the Project Quality Framework proposal. On completing this work it would then be possible to share this with the EU Erasmus+ Team to explore whether or not it would be of value in guiding future Erasmus+ applications, the reviewing process and the impact of project outcomes. Many aspects of the Erasmus+ project application process are well defined, perhaps overly in some cases. This proposal attempts to promote a consideration of the importance of the Quality element and how this can be used to drive the greater impact of Erasmus+ engineering education projects.

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